

United States Department of the Interior

In Reply Refer to:
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FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
Sacramento Fish and Wildlife Office
2800 Cottage Way, Suite W-2605
Sacramento, California 95825-1846

JUL 27 2018

Rick Bottoms, Ph.D.
Chief, Regulatory Division
Attn: Dr. Kevin Schwartz
San Francisco District
U. S. Army Corps of Engineers
1455 Market Street
San Francisco, California 94103-1398

Subject: Formal Consultation on the Santa Clara Valley Water District Stream Maintenance Program (SMP2); 2018 Notice of Proposed Work 1 (2018 NPW1), Santa Clara County, California

Dear Dr. Bottoms:

This letter is in response to your April 4, 2018 letter requesting consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service). The U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (Corps) seeks concurrence from the Service on the effects determinations of ten (10) Santa Clara Valley Water District (SCVWD) Stream Maintenance Program projects and requests them to be appended to the Programmatic Biological Opinion on the SCVWD Stream Maintenance Program (SMP2) in Santa Clara County, California (Service file number 08ESMF00-2012-F-0398) (Programmatic Biological Opinion). Your request was received in our office on April 4, 2018. At issue are the proposed project's effects on the federally listed as endangered California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) (CCR) and salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*) (SMHM) and the federally listed as threatened Pacific coast population of the western snowy plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus nivosus*) (WSP). The Corps determined these projects are either likely to adversely affect or not likely to adversely affect these species. This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act). The California clapper rail was reclassified, and it is now referred to in scientific literature as the California Ridgeway's rail (*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*), but for the purpose of this document we will use the original name, as that remains the listed entity under the Act.

In reviewing the effects of these projects, the Service has relied upon: (1) information contained in your April 4, 2018, letter and (2) the Corps April 4, 2018, email with a spreadsheet "*Enclosure 1- 2018 SCVWD SMP2- NPW1-ESA.pdf*" that covered in detail the rationale for the Corps' effects determinations for each species and project.

Four projects are the application of aquatic herbicides (18-SV-098 Lower Penitencia Creek, 18-SV-165 Guadalupe River, 18-SV-194 Adobe Creek, and 18-SV-168 Guadalupe River). This is not an activity covered in the Programmatic Biological Opinion and, therefore, these projects cannot be appended. Five of the other projects are likely to adversely affect the California clapper rail, salt marsh harvest mouse, and western snowy plover. One project (18-SS-007 Matadero Creek), is not likely to adversely affect the California clapper rail and the salt marsh harvest mouse. The projects are summarized in Table 1.

Based on adverse effects to these species, a 3:1 conservation ratio is applicable per the Programmatic Biological Opinion except for the western snowy plover. Each of these six projects has been listed as a Previously Mitigated Area (PMA) by the SCVWD for the entirety or for a portion of the project area. The Service does not have documentation that these projects are PMAs. Documentation that mitigation has been approved for these areas by the Service shall be provided and verified by the Service prior to beginning work.

Table 1: 2018 NPW1 Projects

Activity	Project	Species Affected	Determinations	Conservation Ratio	PMA
Vegetation Removal < 6"	18-SV-205	SMHM	Likely to Adversely Affect (LAA)	3: 1	PMA
Vegetation Removal < 6"	18-SV-203	CCR, SMHM WSP	LAA	3: 1 for CCR, SMHM	PMA
Vegetation Removal < 6"	18-SV-208	CCR, SMHM WSP	LAA	3: 1 for CCR, SMHM	PMA
Sediment Removal	18-SS-005	CCR	LAA	3: 1	NOT PMA (12500-12600), PMA (12600-17500)
Sediment Removal	18-SS-007	CCR, SMHM	Not Likely to Adversely Affect (NLAA)	Not Applicable	PMA
Sediment Removal	18-SS-004	CCR, WSP	CCR -LAA WSP--NLAA	3: 1 for CCR	NOT PMA (2251-6250), PMA (750-2250)

Of the projects in Table 1, the Corps determined that project areas South of Highway 237 and Highway 101 and East of Highway 880 would Not Likely Adversely Affect the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse and would not require mitigation. The Service concurs with this determination based on:

1. There are known recent occurrences of California clapper rail north of Highway 101, but only one occurrence just south of 101 and along a concrete lined channel. There is low potential for this species to occur South of Highway 237 and Highway 101 and East of Highway 880 and these areas do not provide breeding habitat and do not contain extensive salt marsh habitat needed to support these species. The habitat south of Highway 237 and 101 and east of Highway 880 are significantly different and altered habitat. There is very little vegetation and does not provide cover from predators.
2. Salt marsh harvest mice are known to exist along the flood control levee and edges of sludge lagoons near Coyote Creek, however, they have very low potential to occur South of Highway 237 and Highway 101 and East of Highway 880.
3. All avoidance, minimization, conservation measures, and Best Management Practices (BMPs) as outlined in the Service's Programmatic Biological Opinion, including BMP GEN-11 will be employed for these projects.

Areas North of Highway 237 and Highway 101 may still require mitigation. The Corps identified that the Island Ponds Restoration could potentially be used to compensate for adverse effects to these listed species in these areas, but would need to be proposed by the SCVWD and accepted by the Corps and Service prior to beginning work. In addition, the Corps requires that all Avoidance, Minimization, Conservation Measures, and BMP's as outlined in the Programmatic Biological Opinion for these species be implemented.

The following minimization measures have been incorporated into the project design:

1. There will be minimal ground disturbance associated with work activities.
2. Work will be conducted during daytime hours, during the dry season, after the breeding season, and not within two hours before or after extreme high tides (6.5 feet or above) to minimize and avoid the CCR, SMHM, and WSP.
3. Nesting surveys will be conducted prior to initiation of activities. All ground disturbing activities within WSP habitat (beach, dunes, and habitats within 100 feet of the beach or dunes) will occur outside of the WSP nesting season (March 1 - September 30) to the extent feasible, with no disturbance March 1 – August 31.
4. A biologist will determine presence of species in work area and buffer/delay work activity as needed to accommodate species.
5. Work will be conducted during daytime hours, during the dry season, after the California clapper rail's breeding season, and not within two hours before or after extreme high tides (6.5 feet or above) to minimize and avoid potential impacts to the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse.
6. Day presence/absence surveys will be conducted by a qualified biologist before commencement of work.
7. Work crews would be trained in appropriate Best Management Practice (BMP) measures for species within the work area.
8. All BMP's in the Programmatic Biological Opinion will be implemented, as appropriate.

The vegetation and sediment removal activities were evaluated in the Programmatic Biological Opinion and these proposed projects must fall within the limits specified in the Programmatic Biological Opinion. The Corps and SCVWD shall ensure the amount and extent of the project effects fit within the parameters of the Programmatic Biological Opinion and provide adequate documentation to the Service before the commencement of work. The Service concurs with the Corps determinations and hereby appends these projects to the Programmatic Biological Opinion on the condition that the above are implemented.

If you have any questions regarding this response on these SMP2 projects, please contact Vincent Griego, Senior Biologist, or Ryan Olah, Coast Bay Division Chief, at the letterhead address, electronic mail (Vincent_Griego@fws.gov; Ryan_Olah@fws.gov) or by telephone at (916) 414-6493.

Sincerely,

for
Jennifer M. Norris, Ph.D.
Field Supervisor